

FLPP GigWork DPP

Version 4

Description

Pēdējo divdesmit gadu laikā digitālās platformas - IT uzņēmumi, kas veido un uztur digitālas infrastruktūras cilvēku saskarsmei un dažādu pakalpojumu sniegšanai - ir kļuvušas par ekonomikas un sadzīves neatņemamu sastāvdaļu visā pasaulē. Šo uzņēmumu ietekme ir ne tikai ekonomiska, bet arī sociāli strukturāla. Pētījuma "Digitālajās platformās nodarbināto autonomijas izpratnes un prakse: Wolt un Bolt piegādes darbinieku pieredzes kultūrsocioloģiska analīze", kas veikts no 2022.gada 1.janvārim līdz 2023.gada 31.decembrim, mērķis bija gūt padziļinātu izpratni par vienu šīs jaunās platformu ekonomikas aspektu – platformu darbu (platform labour arī gig work), padziļināti analizējot vienu no visplašāk izplatītākajiem un redzamākajiem platforma darba veidiem – ēdienu piegādes darbu, un kā empīrisko piemēru skatot Rīgā strādājošos ēdienu piegādes kurjerus platformās Wolt un Bolt Food. Pētījuma centrālais analītiskais jautājums bija ar šī jaunā darba formātu saistītā prekaritāte un problemātiskā attiecība starp strādājošo izjusto autonomiju un kontroli. Pētījumā tika izmantotas kvalitatīvās socioloģiskās metodes: 1) tika veiktas 60 padziļinātās intervijas ar platformās strādājošajiem; 2) tika analizēti tiešaistē pieejamie kurjeru savstarpējas saziņas forumu arhīvi (2020-2023); un 3) Bolt Food kurjeriem sūtīto ziņu arhīvs (2020-2023). Pētījuma rezultāti atspoguļoti vairākās zinātniskās publikācijās (tostarp <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.7696> un <https://journal.lu.lv/adz/article/view/2428>).

Over the last twenty years, digital platforms—IT companies that create and maintain digital infrastructures for human interaction and the provision of various services—have become an integral part of the global economy and daily life. The influence of these companies is not only economic but also socially structural. The aim of the research project "The Meaning and Practice of Autonomy in Gig Work: Sociocultural Inquiry in Experience of Wolt and Bolt Delivery Workers in Riga" (conducted from January 1, 2022, to December 31, 2023) was to gain a deeper understanding of one aspect of this new platform economy – gig work – through empirical analysis of food delivery couriers working in Riga for the Wolt and Bolt Food platforms. The central analytical question of the study was the precarity associated with this new form of work and the problematic

relationship between the perceived autonomy of the workers and the control they are subject to. The research utilized qualitative sociological methods: 1) 60 in-depth interviews with platform workers were conducted; and 2) analysis of communication among couriers in Telegram forums; 3) analysis of message sent by Bolt Food to its couriers. The results of the study have been reflected in several scientific publications (including <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.7696> and <https://journal.lu.lv/adz/article/view/2428>).

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Izp-2021/1-0521

Researchers

Iveta Kesane (0000-0002-0151-5407), Maija Spurina (0000-0002-6978-1322)

Organizations

Latvian Academy of Culture

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: FLPP GigWork DPP

Description:

Pēdējo divdesmit gadu laikā digitālās platformas - IT uzņēmumi, kas veido un uztur digitālas infrastruktūras cilvēku saskarsmei un dažādu pakalpojumu sniegšanai - ir kļuvušas par ekonomikas un sadzīves neatņemamu sastāvdaļu visā pasaulē. Šo uzņēmumu ietekme ir ne tikai ekonomiska, bet arī sociāli strukturāla. Pētījuma "Digitālajās platformās nodarbināto autonomijas izpratnes un prakse: Wolt un Bolt piegādes darbinieku pieredzes kultūrsocioloģiska analīze", kas veikts no 2022.gada 1.janvārim līdz 2023.gada 31.decembrim, mērķis bija gūt padziļinātu izpratni par vienu šīs jaunās platformu ekonomikas aspektu – platformu darbu (platform labour arī gig work), padziļināti analizējot vienu no visplašāk izplatītākajiem un redzamākajiem platforma darba veidiem – ēdienu piegādes darbu, un kā empīrisko piemēru skatot Rīgā strādājošos ēdienu piegādes kurjerus platformās Wolt un Bolt Food. Pētījuma centrālais analītiskais jautājums bija ar šī jaunā darba formātu saistītā prekaritāte un problemātiskā attiecība starp strādājošo izjusto autonomiju un kontroli. Pētījumā tika izmantotas kvalitatīvās socioloģiskās metodes: 1) tika veiktas 60 padziļinātās intervijas ar platformās strādājošajiem; 2) tika analizēti tiešaistē pieejamie kurjeru savstarpējas saziņas forumu arhīvi (2020-2023); un 3) Bolt Food kurjeriem sūtīto ziņu arhīvs (2020-2023). Pētījuma rezultāti atspoguļoti vairākās zinātniskās publikācijās (tostarp <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.7696> un <https://journal.lu.lv/adz/article/view/2428>).

Over the last twenty years, digital platforms—IT companies that create and maintain digital infrastructures for human interaction and the provision of various services—have become an integral part of the global economy and daily life. The influence of these companies is not only economic but also socially structural. The aim of the research project "The Meaning and Practice of Autonomy in Gig Work: Sociocultural Inquiry in Experience of Wolt and Bolt Delivery Workers in Riga" (conducted from January 1, 2022, to December 31, 2023) was to gain a deeper understanding of one aspect of this new platform economy – gig work – through empirical analysis of food delivery couriers working in Riga for the Wolt and Bolt Food platforms. The central analytical question of the study was the precarity associated with this new form of work and the problematic relationship between the perceived autonomy of the workers and the control they are subject to. The research utilized qualitative sociological methods: 1) 60 in-depth interviews with platform workers were conducted; and 2) analysis of communication among couriers

in Telegram forums; 3) analysis of message sent by Bolt Food to its couriers. The results of the study have been reflected in several scientific publications (including <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.7696> and <https://journal.lu.lv/adz/article/view/2428>).

Researchers:

Iveta Kesane (0000-0002-0151-5407)

Maija Spurina (0000-0002-6978-1322)

Organizations:

Latvian Academy of Culture

Contact: Spuriņa Maija (maija.spurina@lka.edu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: [lzp-2021/1-0521](#)

Project: [Meaning and Practice of Autonomy in Gig-Work: Sociocultural Inquiry in Experience of Wolt and Bolt Delivery Workers in Riga](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2024-12-01](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[Telegram kanāla "Bolt Food Riga" ziņu arhīvs no 2020. gada janvāra līdz 2023. gada oktobrim.](#)

Datu kopā ietilpst 4513 teksta ziņas, ko platforma Bolt Food nosūtījusi saviem kurjeriem laika posmā no 2020.gada 1.janvāra līdz 2023.gada 31.decembrim saziņas platformā

Telegram. Uz lejuplādes brīdi kanālam bija 7230 lietotāju. Visu ziņu sūtītājs ir Bolt Food Rīga. Ziņas rakstītas latviešu un angļu valodā.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Datu kopā ietilpst 4513 teksta ziņas, ko platforma Bolt Food nosūtījusi saviem kurjeriem laika posmā no 2020.gada 1.janvāra līdz 2023.gada 31.decembrim saziņas platformā Telegram. Uz lejuplādes brīdi kanālam bija 7230 lietotāju. Visu ziņu sūtītājs ir Bolt Food Rīga. Ziņas rakstītas latviešu un angļu valodā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

447

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociologiem, komunikācijas zinātniekiem

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel vai citas tabulāru datu lasīšanas programmas

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

XLS, CSV faili, kas atverami ar programmām, kurās iespējams strādāt ar tabulāriem datiem

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Starptautiski atzīta licence, piemērojama sociālo zinātņu pētījumu ietvaros radītajiem datiem

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Segtas no projekta tiešajām izmaksām pēc nepieciešamības

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

• Ance Kristāla (orcid: [0000-0003-0644-3737](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0644-3737))

• Maija Spurina (0000-0002-6978-1322)

Tiešais atbildīgais par datu ieguvu un sagatavošanu ir projekta vadītājs, par deponēšanu - datu pārvaldības speciālists

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Segtas no projekta tiešajām izmaksām pēc nepieciešamības

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Dati ir publiski pieejami

Dati ir publiski pieejami

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Anonymising data

Dati anonimizēti, lietotāju segvārdus aizvietojo ar identifikācijas numuriem.

Telegram kanāla ziņu arhīvs no 2021. gada 5.jūlija līdz 2023. gada 31.oktobrim.

Datu kopā ietilpst 2609 ziņas, kuras laika posmā no 2021.gada 5.jūlija līdz 2023.gada 31.oktobrim Telegram kanālā nosūtījuši 143 grupas lietotāji. Tostarp 1940 teksta ziņas, 512 transkribētas audio ziņas, 103 attēli, 32 video, 22 digitālās uzlīmes.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Datu kopā ietilps 3486 ziņas, kuras laika posmā no 2023.gada 26.septembra līdz 2023.gada 1.novembrim Telegram kanālā nosūtījuši 59 kanāla lietotāji. Tostarp 1828 teksta ziņas, 1365 transkribētas audioziņas, 246 attēli, 36 video un 11 digitālas uzlīmes.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

311

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociologiem, komunikācijas zinātniekiem

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel vai citas tabulāru datu lasīšanas programmas

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

XLS, CSV faili, kas atverami ar programmām, kurās iespējams strādāt ar tabulāriem datiem

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Starptautiski atzīta licence, piemērojama sociālo zinātņu pētījumu ietvaros radītajiem datiem

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Segtas no projekta tiešajām izmaksām pēc nepieciešamības

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

• Ance Kristāla (orcid: [0000-0003-0644-3737](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0644-3737))

• Maija Spurina (0000-0002-6978-1322)

Tiešais atbildīgais par datu iegūvi un sagatavošanu ir projekta vadītājs, par deponēšanu - datu pārvaldības speciālists

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Segtas no projekta tiešajām izmaksām pēc nepieciešamības

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Dati ir publiski pieejami

Dati ir publiski pieejami

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Anonymising data

Dati anonimizēti, lietotāju segvārdus aizvietojoit identifikācijas numuriem.

Telegram kanāla ziņu arhīvs no 2023. gada 26.septembra līdz 2023. gada 31.oktobrim

Datu kopā ietilps 3486 ziņas, kuras laika posmā no 2023.gada 26.septembra līdz 2023.gada 1.novembrim Telegram kanālā nosūtījuši 59 kanāla lietotāji. Tostarp 1828 teksta ziņas, 1365 transkribētas audioziņas, 246 attēli, 36 video un 11 digitālas uzlīmes.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Datu kopā ietilpst 2609 ziņas, kuras laika posmā no 2021.gada 5.jūlija līdz 2023.gada 31.oktobrim Telegram kanālā "Bolt Food Wolt Riga" nosūtījuši 143 grupas lietotāji. Tostarp 1940 teksta ziņas, 512 transkribētas audio ziņas, 103 attēli, 32 video, 22 digitālās uzlīmes.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

408

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociologiem, komunikācijas zinātniekiem

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel vai citas tabulāru datu lasīšanas programmas

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

XLS, CSV faili, kas atverami ar programmām, kurās iespējams strādāt ar tabulāriem datiem

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Starptautiski atzīta licence, piemērojama sociālo zinātņu pētījumu ietvaros radītajiem datiem

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Segtas no projekta tiešajām izmaksām pēc nepieciešamības

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

• Ance Kristāla (orcid: [0000-0003-0644-3737](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0644-3737))

• Maija Spurina (0000-0002-6978-1322)

Tiešais atbildīgais par datu iegūvi un sagatavošanu ir projekta vadītājs, par deponēšanu - datu pārvaldības speciālists

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Segtas no projekta tiešajām izmaksām pēc nepieciešamības

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Dati ir publiski pieejami

Dati ir publiski pieejami

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Anonymising data

Dati anonimizēti, lietotāju segvārdus aizvietojoit identifikācijas numuriem.

Interviju ar Wolt un Bolt Food Rīgā nodarbinātajiem ēdienu kurjeriem transkripti

Datu kopā ietilpst 60 transkripti intervijām ar ēdienu piegādes platformās Wolt un Bolt Food nodarbinātajiem kurjeriem Rīgā.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Datu kopā ietilpst 60 transkripti intervijām ar ēdienu piegādes platformās Wolt un Bolt Food nodarbinātajiem kurjeriem Rīgā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Šāda satura dati iepriekš Latvijā nav iegūti

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo zinātņu pētniekiem, antropologiem, nodarbinātības pētniekiem, ekonomistiem

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

Dati netiks publicēti.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Interviju transkripcijas to sensitīvā satura dēļ nav publiski pieejamas.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Teksta dokuments .doc formātā, atvērt ar MS Word vai līdzīgām programmām

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Starptautiski atzīta licence, piemērojama valsts pētījumu programmu ietvaros radītajiem datiem

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Dati nav publiski pieejami.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Ance Kristāla (orcid: [0000-0003-0644-3737](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0644-3737))
- Maija Spurina (0000-0002-6978-1322)

Tiešais atbildīgais par datu iegūvi un sagatavošanu ir projekta vadītājs, par deponēšanu - datu pārvaldības speciālists

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Physical access control

Dati glabājas Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī un ir pieejami tikai projekta pētniekiem.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Personīgas, sensitīvas informācijas paušana

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Transkripcijās dzēsta visa informāciju, kas ļautu identificēt respondentu: respondenta vārdu un konkrētas atsauces uz vietām vai institūcijām biogrāfijā, kas ļautu respondentu identificēt.

Powered by

